

EHDEN

EUROPEAN HEALTH DATA & EVIDENCE NETWORK

806968 – EHDEN

European Health Data & Evidence Network

WP6 – Outreach and Sustainability

D6.1 Stakeholder mapping

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DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Description
V1.0	29 January 2019	First Draft
V1.1	16 April 2019	Second draft
V1.2	6 May 2019	Third draft
V1.3	8 May 2019	Revised Version for formal review
V2	21 May 2019	Updated version for consortium review
V2	12 Jun 2019	Final version for submission

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DEFINITIONS

Participants of the EHDEN Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

EMC	Erasmus Universitair Medisch Centrum Rotterdam- The Netherlands (Project Coordinator)
Synapse	Synapse Research Management Partners S.L. - Spain
UOXF	The Chancellor, Masters and Scholars of the University of Oxford - United Kingdom
UTARTU	Tartu Ulikool - Estonia
UAVR	Universidade de Aveiro – Portugal
The Hyve	The Hyve BV – the Netherlands
Odysseus	Odysseus Data Services SRO – Czech Republic
EPF	Forum Europeen des Patients (FPE) - Luxembourg
NICE	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence – United Kingdom
UMC	Stiftelsen WHO Collaborating Centre for International Drug Monitoring - Sweden
ICHOM	International Consortium for Health Outcomes measurement LTD - United Kingdom
Janssen	Janssen Pharmaceutica NV - Belgium (Project Lead)
Pfizer	Pfizer Limited – United Kingdom
Abbvie	AbbVie Inc - United States
IRIS	Institut De Recherches Internationales Servier - France
SARD	Sanofi Aventis Recherche & Developpement - France
Bayer	Bayer Aktiengesellschaft - Germany
Lilly	Eli Lilly and Company Limited – United Kingdom
AZ	AstraZeneca AB - Sweden
Novartis	Novartis Pharma AG - Switzerland
UCB	UCB Biopharma SPRL - Belgium
Celgene	Celgene Management SARL - Switzerland

Grant agreement	The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the IMI JU for the undertaking of the EHDEN project (806968).
Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
Consortium	The EHDEN Consortium, comprising the above-mentioned legal entities.
Consortium agreement	Agreement concluded amongst EHDEN participants for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

This deliverable provides an overview WP6 strategy for Outreach and sustainability and the workflow created in this WP.

In addition, the creation of the EHDEN Stakeholder Registry was created in order to have a wide view of all Stakeholders who might be interested in EHDEN and to apply to the calls. The Registry has been enabled by means of an online application for EHDEN partners for internal use.

Finally, a first analysis of the current status of the Registry with 67 entries gives an overview of the current distribution per category, status, as well as country distribution.

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1. INTRODUCTION: WP6 WORKFLOW

The overall aim of Work Package 6 (WP6), Outreach and Sustainability, is to support the main objective of EHDEN: To create an ecosystem where the use of real world data is enabled by a common data model and an open infrastructure across a substantial and varied set of European data users and providers that can operate in a federated fashion. To achieve this, three main pillars have been devised:

1. Convincing stakeholders to be involved in EHDEN activities
2. Sustainability efforts to iteratively design, discuss and implement a plan for a long-term self-sustainability of EHDEN activities
3. Community building, encompassing all key stakeholders

WP6 has defined a workflow describing all steps to be achieved (Figure 1). According to the workflow, a first step is to define an initial list of stakeholders' types, including the priority of each category and the objectives of the outreach. For the main stakeholder types, specific value propositions (VP) will be developed, taking into account the different factors that may affect their active participation. The evolving nature of this workflow will enable the refinement of the strategic approaches to facilitate the engagement of external parties. All consortium members will be able to contribute to this common goal leveraging their extensive, existing networks of contacts, of all academia and EFPIA partners, providing each type of stakeholder with a list of institutions they consider to be essential for the development of an active EHDEN community. From the selected group, and the value propositions defined, specific outreach teams will be constructed aimed at approaching specific groups. These outreach teams will get instructions on how to approach the different stakeholders, instructions to be developed by WP6 by developing Value Propositions. Finally, within the WP, all interactions will be tracked, as feedback will be collected in order to assess and improve the success rate of these outreach efforts.

FIGURE 1. WP6 OUTREACH WORKFLOW

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2. STAKEHOLDER MAPPING

The identification of EHDEN stakeholders and their differing levels of participation plays a key role in achieving successful project outcomes. Participation requirements, however, are not the same for everyone associated with the project. Instead, participation expectations depend on the degree of a project stakeholder’s direct or indirect involvement. Because of this, it is vital to a project's successful completion to accurately identify project stakeholders, set participation expectations and communicate accordingly.

This deliverable aims to report on the different stakeholders’ types that will need a value proposition (VP) for successful outreach, including if necessary, sub-categories.

To this purpose, the Project Description of Action (DoA) proposed a list of all the key stakeholder types that could be approached, so that appropriate value propositions could be developed. The expectation was that at least these would include:

- Data sources/data custodians
- SMEs/service and tool developers
- Regulatory/payer/HTA agencies
- Patient representatives
- Health authorities/healthcare providers
- Patient representatives
- Academic researchers
- Pharmaceutical and related industries
- European research infrastructures
- Non-profit science institutions
- Funding agencies and charities

A first discussion around stakeholders was held during the WP leads kick-off meeting in November 2018, in which the order of the list above was defined. According to the nature of EHDEN and the calls to be launched, it was agreed that the project would initially liaise with 3 types of stakeholders in a first outreaching exercise: data sources, SME, regulatory/HTA.

3. STAKEHOLDER REGISTRY

After the consultation done with all consortium members, a Stakeholder Registry tool was created using SharePoint to capture all members’ input, using their know network of contacts.

FIGURE 2. STAKEHOLDER REGISTRY SCREENSHOT

Some conclusions were shared with the whole Consortium via the EHDEN Forum, where comments were shared and new feedback was generated, enabling the refinement of an initial list of stakeholders’ types. This list is meant to evolve throughout the whole duration of the project, adapting to the different stages of

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EHDEN. After final refinement within WP6, a revised list of stakeholders was defined, which allowed a more granular structure, namely:

- Academic Researchers
- Disease cohort
- European Research Infrastructures
- Funding agencies and charities
- GP Database
- Health Authorities
- Hospital
- Hospital Network
- HTA Agencies
- IMI BD4BO projects
- Non-profit Science institutes
- Patient representatives
- Payers
- Pharmaceutical industry
- Policy makers
- Regulatory
- Small to Medium Enterprise
- Other

The Stakeholder Registry allows to have a complete view for each Stakeholder registered by entering the following information:

- Institution name
- Category: drop down menu from the list above
- Country
- Information: to include useful information for the outreach team
- Website
- Contact person
- Email
- Who suggested the Stakeholder
- Stakeholder status: to select from the following:
 - o Potential: Stakeholders who we know or have references for, and that could be interested, but have not had any discussion with about EHDEN. This would be the main target for WP6 outreach efforts.
 - o Contacted: Stakeholders that are one step further, with whom preliminary/informal discussions have been held but without nothing definite. There is ongoing work for WP6.
 - o Engaged: intending or having applied to a grant, or having participated in meetings, active members of OHDSI, etc. WP6 would keep track of these.
- Updates: field aimed at tracking the interactions done with the Stakeholder

In the next pages, the application to enter a new Stakeholder is shown; in addition, a template in Excel has also been developed (see Annex 1 – Stakeholder Registry).

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Save Cancel Copy link

New item

Institution Name *

Enter value here

Category *

▼

Select the Stakeholder Category. You can add a new category if no good match can be found.

Country *

Enter value here

Information

Enter value here

Provide some information about the Stakeholder that could be useful for the outreach team. This can include the rationale.

Website

Enter a URL

Enter display text

FIGURE 3. STAKEHOLDER REGISTRY ENTRY (PART 1)

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Contact Person *
Enter value here

Email *
Enter value here

Suggested By
Enter a name or email address

Select the user that suggested the Stakeholder

Stakeholder Status *
Potential ▼

Priority
Normal ▼

Updates
Enter value here

Interactions with the Stakeholder over time can be added here. This will automatically be timestamped.

Attachments
[Add attachments](#)

Save **Cancel**

FIGURE 4. STAKEHOLDER REGISTRY ENTRY (PART 2)

4. STAKEHOLDERS ANALYSIS

As of 21st of May 2019, the Registry has been filled with 67 entries, and WP6 team is reaching out to all partners to further extend the list.

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The first graphic below shows the distribution per category. The most frequent stakeholder is the SME which is driven by the first Open Call for training and certification on mapping health data from various formats to the OMOP common data model. The second category corresponds to Hospital Network, who would be able to apply to next call for Data sources wishing to map their data.

FIGURE 5. STAKEHOLDERS DISTRIBUTED PER CATEGORY

A second distribution of the Registry entries corresponds to their status, by which we see a higher value of the “engaged” status, showing a high number of applicants to 1st Open Call, as well as other Stakeholders who are already planning to apply to future calls. In addition, project partners are also having discussions with interested parties for the to the EHDEN calls.

FIGURE 6. STAKEHOLDERS DISTRIBUTED PER STATUS

If we analyse the distribution per country, we can see a wide spectrum across Europe, with some higher values which coincide with project partners’ countries. This distribution goes in line with the geographical spread seen in the applications received within the SME Pilot call.

FIGURE 7. STAKEHOLDERS DISTRIBUTED PER COUNTRY

A full list of all stakeholders currently in the register will be provided to IMI with the yearly report.

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5. NEXT STEPS

The Stakeholder compilation is perceived as a standing activity, that will be active during the full duration of the project; however, the completion of the Registry in the initial phases is of utmost importance, as this will contribute to all the outreach activities to be performed by EHDEN.

Our next step is to actively contact all EHDEN partners to populate the stakeholder library. The inclusion of the contacts from all these 22 EHDEN partners will result in a large valuable network of stakeholders that will drive the development and sustainability of the EHDEN ecosystem in Europe.

ANNEXES

Annex 1 – Stakeholder Registry

ID	Owner/Initiator	Institution Name	Country	Category	Stakeholder Status	Priority	Contact Person	Contact Person Email	Website	Information	Comments
1											
2											
3											
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